

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reduction of Peroxydisulphate by Ascorbic Acid

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The kinetics of the reduction of peroxydisulphate by ascorbic acid has been studied in an acidic medium. The rate of reduction has a direct dependence on the concentration of peroxydisulphate and is independent of ascorbic acid concentration. The influence of neutral salts is negligible while that of acidity is slightly retarding. Allyl acetate inhibits strongly and suggests the formation of sulphate (SO_4^-) radical ions. A chain mechanism, initiated by the decomposition of peroxydisulphate, has been proposed which involves the intermediate formation of hydroxyl and ascorbate free radicals.

The strong reducing properties of ascorbic acid and its subsequent use as an analytical reagent, have been reviewed by Erdey and Svehla¹. By mild oxidising agents ascorbic acid is oxidised to dehydroascorbic acid (A)².

Several recent publications have described the reductions by ascorbic acid from the kinetic standpoint, some of which have been directed towards the catalytic reduction³. Grinstead⁴ has shown that the rate determining step during the reduction of EDTA. Iron (III) chelate is the one electron oxidation of ascorbic acid to the ascorbate radical. In presence of hydrogen peroxide the reduction involved a chain process. Khan and Martell⁵ investigated the kinetics of the uncatalysed, copper (II) and iron (III) catalysed oxidation of ascorbic acid by molecular oxygen in the pH range 2-5.5 and found the monoionic ascorbic acid as the main reacting species. The catalysed oxidations were explained on the basis of formation of complexes between catalysts and ascorbic acid. Recently the reduction of palladium⁶, hexacyanoferrate (III)⁷, platinum (IV) and osmium (VIII)⁸ by ascorbic acid has also been investigated.

In the present communication the results of the uncatalysed reduction of peroxydisulphate with ascorbic acid have been reported and the kinetic experimental data obtained has been utilised in formulating a suitable mechanism governing the reduction process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solutions of potassium peroxydisulphate and ascorbic acid were prepared fresh by dissolving dry crystals of the E. Merck, pronanalysis samples of the reagent. Sulphuric acid used was a BDH sample of AnalaR grade. All other chemicals used were of extra

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pure quality. Bi-distilled water was used during the preparation of all the solutions and for all dilutions where necessary. Glass vessels used were of Jena glass and were coated from outside with Japan black.

Requisite amounts of the solutions of potassium peroxydisulphate and sulphuric acid, taken in a Jena reaction bottle were placed in a water thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. Calculated amount of the solution of ascorbic acid was transferred to start the reaction. Progress of the kinetics was followed by estimating the amount of unconsumed ascorbic acid by titrating against standard solution of iodine. From the amount of ascorbic acid consumed zero order rate constants were calculated directly. First order rate constants to peroxydisulphate were calculated by changing the ascorbic acid concentration in terms of peroxydisulphate via stoichiometry.

RESULTS

Stoichiometry: Reaction mixture containing 0.012M peroxydisulphate, $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ sulphuric acid and $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ascorbic acid was allowed to react for 10 hrs at 40°. The amount of peroxydisulphate consumed was found to be identical with the concentration of ascorbic acid and thus corresponds to the following stoichiometric equation:

Dehydroascorbic acid was detected as the product of the reaction⁹.

Dependence on the Oxidising and Reducing Agent: In order to ascertain the order of the reaction with respect to oxidising and the reducing agent the kinetics was followed at different initial concentrations of ascorbic acid and peroxydisulphate. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Peroxydisulphate and Ascorbic Acid Dependence^a

Peroxydisulphate M	Ascorbic acid M × 10 ³	$k_0 \times 10^{2b}$ mole min ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^{4c}$ min ⁻¹
0.012	4.0	7.1	26.1
0.012	3.0	6.8	24.2
0.012	2.0	7.2	25.3
0.012	1.0	7.0	24.8
0.016	4.0	10.0	26.5
0.020	4.0	11.3	23.7
0.024	4.0	14.2	23.9
0.016	3.0	9.1	23.9
0.020	3.0	11.8	24.8
0.024	3.0	13.8	23.9
0.016	2.0	9.9	26.0
0.020	2.0	12.3	25.6
0.024	2.0	15.0	26.0

a. $H_2SO_4 = 10^{-3}M$ and Temperature = 30°.

b. Zero order constants to ascorbic acid.

c. Unimolecular constants to peroxydisulphate.

It is evident from the table 1 that the zero order rate constants to ascorbic acid (k_0) are fairly constant at constant concentration of peroxydisulphate, but increase linearly with the concentration of peroxydisulphate. The zero order dependence in ascorbic acid is also supported by the linear plot of ascorbic acid concentration (c) vs time (t) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.—Plot of 'c' versus 't'.

$K_2S_2O_8$ concentration : (1) $2.4 \times 10^{-2}M$; (2) $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$; (3) $1.6 \times 10^{-2}M$ and (4) $1.2 \times 10^{-2}M$.

In the last column of Table 1 unimolecular constants (k_1) have been calculated which show fairly concordant values at all concentrations of peroxydisulphate and ascorbic acid. It is, therefore, concluded that the reaction is of first order to peroxydisulphate and of zero order to ascorbic acid and the average value of k_1 is $24.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$ in $10^{-3}M$ H_2SO_4 at 30° .

Dependence on neutral salts : The effect of addition of potassium chloride and potassium sulphate was studied. The results are summarised in Table 2.

It is observed from the table 2 that addition of neutral salts results in a slight increase in the rate constants.

Dependence on Acid Concentration : The investigations were carried out at six different concentrations of sulphuric acid. Table 3 presents the results of the effect of acidity on the rate of reduction of peroxydisulphate by ascorbic acid.

TABLE 2

Neutral Salts Dependence^a

KCl <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^4$ min^{-1}	$k_2\text{SO}_4$ <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^4$ min^{-1}
0.0	26.5	0.0	26.5
0.015	26.9	0.005	26.7
0.030	27.2	0.010	27.0
0.060	27.9	0.020	27.9

a. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.016M$; Ascorbic acid = $4 \times 10^{-3}M$;
 $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 10^{-3}M$ and Temperature = 30° .

TABLE 3

Sulphuric Acid Dependence^a

H_2SO_4 <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^4$ min^{-1}
5×10^{-4}	29.5
1×10^{-3}	26.5
2×10^{-3}	23.7
3×10^{-3}	21.6
4×10^{-3}	19.8
5×10^{-3}	18.6

a. Conditions same as in Table 2.

A perusal of the above table shows that a ten fold increase in sulphuric acid concentration results in almost one-third decrease in the rate constant. It may, therefore, be concluded that H^+ ion has a slightly inhibitory effect on the reaction rate.

Dependence on Temperature: The reduction of peroxydisulphate by ascorbic acid showed quite a prominent effect of temperature. The overall unimolecular rate constants at 30° , 35° , 40° and 45° were calculated as 12.9, 25.1, 44.7 and $85.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{min}^{-1}$ respectively. From the above data the magnitudes of the temperature coefficient, frequency factor, energy and entropy of activation have been found out as 3.43, $1.9 \times 10^{12} \text{litre mole}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$, 23.6 Kcals and -3.33 e.u. respectively.

Allyl Acetate Inhibition: The strong inhibitory action of allyl acetate has been demonstrated by the fact that a reaction, which proceeded upto 50% in a certain time, was reduced to 30% and 18% in presence of 4% and 10% allyl acetate respectively.

DISCUSSION

The reduction of peroxydisulphate by ascorbic acid is a two electron transfer reaction in which ascorbic acid is oxidised to dehydroascorbic acid. It has already been established by earlier workers that ascorbic acid exists as ascorbate ion in aqueous solution which are mainly responsible for the great reducing action. In an acidic medium the equation may be represented as :

The primary step in all oxidations involving peroxydisulphate is its symmetrical decomposition into two sulphate radical ions¹⁰, followed by several consecutive reactions forming a chain. For the reduction of peroxidisulphate, by ascorbic acid following chain mechanism has been proposed, which involves the intermediate formation of ascorbate free radical (AH⁻):

where A represents the product dehydroascorbic acid. Assuming steady-state conditions with respect to $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, AH^{\cdot} and OH^{\cdot} , the rate of decomposition of peroxydisulphate may be obtained as follows :

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = \left(\frac{k_{1b}k_2k_4}{k_5} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \quad (6)$$

The above rate law equation (6) clearly explains that the reduction of peroxydisulphate by ascorbic acid will follow first order disappearance in peroxydisulphate and will be independent of ascorbic acid concentrations. This is, therefore, in accordance to our experimental observations.

The formation of sulphate radical ion ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) is supported by the strong inhibitory effect of allyl acetate which is known as an efficient capture agent for these ions. The existence of ascorbate and hydroxyl radical as intermediate has been postulated by Grinstead (loc. cit.) during the EDTA-Fe(III) chelate catalysed reduction of hydrogen peroxide by ascorbic acid. The small inhibitory effect of acidity is ascribed, to the formation of free H^+ ions during the propagation and termination of the chain.

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